

Appendix 1

Passenger Flow with a vehicle

Transparency

5 Traceability

Human centric (e.g. training, requirements, needs, goals, regulations)

Traceability for boarded people in the vehicle+ vehicle	"As a security officer who got contacted by the police about a certain car, I want to track where the car was seen last, so that I can predict where it is going next.	An intelligent system connected to the video surveillance in the terminal can be given parameters to search for the current or latest location of a vehicle or person in the terminal by being given the register plate, a photo of a person, or other such identifying data.
	As a security officer who got contacted by the police about a certain passenger, I want to be able to get help from an AI system in tracking down a certain face, so that the person can be stopped within the terminal."	

If anything goes wrong, that I can find help at any stage to rectify issues	As a passenger with a vehicle, I want to have a helpline information (phone number etc.) that I can use when something goes wrong.	Terminal area and booking documents and booking app contains the help information (for different purposes broken down).
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It should be transparent from the customers' and port's point-of-view - why their car is being processed by the port and what information?	As a passenger, I want to know exactly what information about my vehicle and implicitly, me, is being processed by the port, so I can feel safe and informed.	Before a person with a vehicle enters the port, they are given explanation of what information will be handled, for example at the stage of making a reservation when they agree to give the necessary information of their vehicle
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Managing the complexity of traceability and GDPR	As a technically oriented passenger, I want to know and have the data available only for me of what data of my car is handled by AI so that I know the decisions concerning my car is made by AI and not a terminal personnel.	A clear advertisement is placed on the booking document about the AI and data privacy.
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Crisis management for instances in which everyone wants their information erased	System administrator I want to manage the GDPR requirements in efficient manner so that the service is not jammed by the user information request or erase request	Data information policy is communicated at the service app/web page. Procedures in place for GDPR compliance and required steps are planned for example huge amount of user data request. For example redirection of resources or waiting times are clearly communicated.
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Technology or Practicality centric (e.g. testing, back-up, systems, logistics)

External systems related to vehicles might be need to take into account	As a driver of a modern vehicle, I want to make sure that no port system will confuse or abuse any other system in my vehicle, e.g. bluetooth or self-driving systems, so that I can still trust my vehicle when entering the port	No feature of the smart terminal or port must interfere in an unwanted way with any system in the passenger vehicles.
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If there is automation how is the car indentation done and how are errors handled	AS a driver, I want to know how to drive into the ship to right place so that the ship is stowed efficiently, and where all the booked vehicles can fit without any problems.	Car indentation system (digital, semi-automated, etc.) with control, navigation and markings is placed in the car deck to direct cars in line and to right places.
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How to count people in the car	As a port official, I want to be able to reliably and automatically know how many passengers are traveling in one vehicle, so that the border control is secure	The system has a reliable way to detect people sitting in a vehicle, that is in balance with respecting the privacy of passengers and adhering to border protocols
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traceability for the flow from an even passenger count	As a port official, in the case of a seemingly failed passenger count performed by the system, I want to be able to track the possible time of the error so that the cause can be found and the error corrected	The system is transparent in its functioning and marks possible "uncertain" situations with timestamps or other identifying information
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traceability for the flow from an even passenger count	As a frequent sea traffic passenger with my own car, I want to know that my car is not mixed with some other misbehaving (e.g. criminal etc.) drivers car, so that I can trust the system and continue to choose the company that I have used to.	Car identification system is tested with right and wrong data and error handling is defined in the terminal action plan and terminal personnel is trained with error handling
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Data & information centric

Can the passengers trace their data? Do they have access? --> right to access and right to erase according to GDPR	As a passenger wanting to know what data about me is handled, I want to be able to get access to my data held in the system and get it erased, so that I have autonomy and agency over my data.	The data tied to a person can be found and is erasable in the system upon request.
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Data

7 Privacy and Data

Human centric (e.g. training, requirements, needs, goals, regulations)

What is within the parameters of the terminal's responsibility	As an official of safety, I want to know, who to contact in terms of misbehaviour so that safety is ensured in all cases.	Smart terminal area is defined in the blueprints of the SMARTER project with responsibilities and roles.
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Could there be privacy problems	As a passenger, I want to make sure that my data is not unnecessarily stored in the system so that it can't be misused or stolen.	The data storing and collecting follows the GDPR regulations and identifying data is anonymized or destroyed within the legal time frame.
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What happens if passengers deny permission? - -> deny access to service?	As a booking site manager, I want to make sure that the passengers have agreed to the terms and conditions before booking their journey, so no laws are violated when they enter the terminal.	Before being able to finish purchasing tickets, the passenger is required to accept the terms and conditions of using the smart terminal and having the minimum required data collected.
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Technology or Practicality centric (e.g. testing, back-up, systems, logistics)

Providing arrival time information for the cars	As a car stevedorer, I want to give time information on digital boards or on apps how the ship stowage is proceeding to avoid multiple inquiries on the subject	Communication plan has a section about on-time communication for different logistical purposes towards car carriers
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there might be applications which utilize vehicle information and are not related to passenger flow	As a vehicle owner, I want to know, where my vehicle information is used so that it is not used in matters where it doesn't have my consent.	Data consent lifecycle is defined in the SMART terminal blueprints.
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Data & information centric

What new data does the car provide?	As a former passenger without a driver's license and now with a license I want to know and see some visible information about the flow of events with the car when entering the harbor because I haven't experienced the passenger flow with a vehicle before and I'm a little bit nervous.	Harbor area will have clear signs of the data requirements and visualize the flow of events.
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Safety & Security

#12 System Security System Safety

Human centric(e.g. training, requirements, needs, goals, regulations)

Humans are not good at following instructions	As a passenger, I want the process to be as simple as possible, so that I can smoothly board the ship without having to worry about following complicated instructions in a potentially high-pressure situation.	The boarding process is as similar to what it used to be as possible, or even simpler. Any and all instructions are crystal clear so that the passengers are able to proceed without asking for assistance as often as possible.
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Delay can cause people to the actions to their own hands	As a border control personnel, I want to be prepared for delays with the ship turnaround so that I know what to do with passengers behaviour in those situations.	Action plan for personnels in terms of delays are embedded into the logistics plan and it will have a section on human behaviour with smart system delays and actions preventing misbehaviour on passengers.
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Technology or Practicality centric (e.g. testing,back-up, systems, logistics)

Overbooking?	As a passenger with my family in our vehicle, I would like to know the capacity of the system before hand so I can avoid a situation where it is overbooked so that I do not turn up and not be able to use the service	The system can display capacity information for passengers that access the service remotely and at the port, display terminals can also provide these types of information for passengers.
System integrations to harbor services	As a system administrator, I would like the system to be easily integrated so that passengers driving into the port can easily access information	Clear logs that shows the state of the system and provide appropriate feedback and APIs that can improve system integration.
Can normal cameras capture everything?	As a surveillance system developer, I want to know the parameters and attributes of the cameras so I can develop a surveillance system that security can use and rely on.	Technical data of the camera is communicated to developers and also to wider audience in order to built trust on the system as a whole
vehicles add more external systems which are connected to the 'terminal'/passenger flow system and introduce more work to cover system security aspects	As a surveillance system developer, I want to have the breakdown of different use case ascenarious of the system so that I can develop the surveillance system to serve peoples safety.	Different use cases in passenger flows are modeled and communicated to all needed participants torugh the development lifecycle.

<p>If there is an accident, what happens? Cannot read plate numbers? Snowy? Someone blocks platenumbers...</p>	<p>"As a passenger, I want the new system to not make boarding any more inconvenience for me, so that I can board the ship with my vehicle just like before (or hopefully even faster).</p>	<p>Passengers are instructed to clear their register plates before arriving to the terminal. An employee is still present to resolve problem situations (e.g. to quickly clean the register plate if needed). Accidents are handled as they currently are when two human drivers are involved. For accident situations with smart vehicles, accountability is also determined by the smart vehicle's accountability.</p>
	<p>As a passenger, I want it to be clear what should happen if there is a problem situation, so that I can board the ship with my vehicle just like before (or hopefully even faster)."</p>	

<p>Passengers with smarter vehicles: potential risks</p>	<p>As a passenger with a smart vehicle, I want to make sure that the systems in the terminal don't maliciously affect my vehicle and vice versa, so that I can use the smart terminal safely.</p>	<p>If the terminal interacts with smart vehicles, it must be in a way that does not compromise the safety of either party. There must be clear limits to what data is shared and what permissions the systems have for information exchange.</p>
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<p>How does the smart harbor handle smart vehicles</p>	<p>As a passenger in a Smart vehicle in Smart harbor, I want to be sure that I manage to get into the ship safely with my vehicle so that I can go and book a trip for my whole family.</p>	<p>Smart harbor follows a protocol on traditional cars and a smart vehicles when developing the flow of events from harbor entering to entering to the ship.</p>
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13 System Safety Audi

Technology or Practicality centric (e.g. testing, back-up, systems, logistics)

<p>how to handle the lithium batteries</p>	<p>As an EV driver, I want to know, if I need to take any extra procedures on my car before entering to the terminal area or to the ship.</p>	<p>Boarding pass on cars are shared with instructions for different vehicles.</p>
<p>Failure (traffic light etc.) - failure to recognise the right vehicle --> what happens to ship loading or unloading?</p>	<p>"As a passenger driving his car at the harbor with my family, I would like an alternative system in place if traffic lights fail so I am not stuck in a traffic jam with my family as this can cause stress. As the traffic operator in charge of operating traffic lights for ship loading and unloading, I would like an alternative system if traffic lights fail so that I can continue with ship loading and unloading."</p>	<p>The system can provide a standby system in place should the traffic lights fail or a human traffic warden that will help direct traffic for ship loading and unloading.</p>
<p>When you get off ship there are police and check-points, for alcohol --> ways of assisting police?</p>	<p>"As a passenger coming off the ship I would like to be quickly checked by the police so that I can disembark the ship on time As a police officer checking passengers at the check point, I would like a system that helps me quickly and efficiently to scan passengers ."</p>	<p>Digital scanners that synchronize passenger information with regulations such as alcohol limits that can be brought in and to ensure that drunk or underage passengers are not driving.</p>

Data & information centric

<p>From the safety perspective - we want to know that we are getting the right, accurate information</p>	<p>"As a passenger with a vehicle, I would like to know that I have accurate information for me and my vehicle so I am not misinformed or violate any regulations.</p> <p>As the information officer, I would like the system that provides information to passengers to be always up to date and accurate so that I can provide accurate information to the passengers and their vehicles to avoid any stress loss of information can cause."</p>	<p>Regular digital or even manual information system checks with prompts informing on current updates such as parking information, duration of parking, etc.</p>
<p>Means of verification - authentication of information</p>	<p>"As a passenger with a vehicle, I would like me and my vehicle to be authenticated so that I can leave harbor when I have to and not have any cause for a case of mistaken identity.</p>	<p>Digital verification devices such as number plate scanners for vehicles to ensure that vehicle is authentic and in line with regulations and biometric scanner for human passengers.</p>

Accountability

18 Auditability

Human centric(e.g. training, requirements, needs, goals, regulations)

Vehicles increase work on auditability, due to vehicles and systems needed for those locally and externally	As the person in charge of registering all the vehicles that use the port, I need to be able to accurately record how many vehicles register online or in person and to reconcile that with the number that make the trip.	APIs and Interoperable systems that can provide accurate data records from different terminals and can synchronize efficiently with the ports system
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Is the booking different?	As a passenger driving into the port, I need to know that the information that I get from remote terminals is clear and the same as the one provided at the port gate so that I avoid any ambiguity or wrong information	System provides clear and transparent information without any ambiguity at remote terminals and at digital terminals and with people who check in passengers at the port.
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Technology or Practicality centric (e.g. testing, back-up, systems, logistics)

Attention to be placed on data management system - can AI be used for identifying relevant information for relevant parties?	"As a passenger with special needs and my vehicle adapted to suit me, I would like pertinent information for me and my vehicle to aid my use of the harbor.	AI integrated into the system that can help identify data patterns for users with special needs and provide necessary information.
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Data & information centric

Can effective data consent systems be HCI of the future? --> can consent span the entire passenger experience?	As a driver of a SMART vehicle using the terminal, I would like a situation where the system can connect with my vehicle and communicate my data consent to me using voice and for me to give consent in the same manner.	A clear and well defined HCI system where voice can be used to communicate data consent in line with relevant regulations.
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<p>Its not just the terminal operator - border control, guard, police, passengers --> data should be available for all these parties</p>	<p>As a user of the system in any of the capacities mentioned, I would like an aggregated system that gives me access to relevant data or information that I would need to carry out my duties</p>	<p>A centralized data management system with clearly outlined details on access rights and clear logs on users.</p>
<p>Passenger information: when booking for truck journey, driver's info is not confirmed, unlike in passenger traffic.</p>	<p>As a safety officer at the SMart terminal, I want to be aware that all passenger are identified with appropriate identification documents, so that I can do my job properly and responsible.</p>	<p>Booking information does not exclude anyone from the needed identification information and the booking application has the identification information as a mandatory field.</p>

Passenger Flow without a vehicle

Transparency

5 Traceability

Human centric (e.g. training, requirements, needs, goals, regulations)

<p>Avoiding risks brought up by bias</p>	<p>As a passenger, I want to have smoothly pass at the security check, so that I will not be stopped because of my race, gender, age, etc qualities</p>	<p>Ensure the quality of the data by testing. Testing at least with race, gender, age should be done and variance between gropes should not be significant. Realtime testing in real context needs to be done before launch.</p>
<p>Ability to show where we have come from and where have been.</p>	<p>As a passenger I dont want to get lost in the terminal so that I wont be late from my cruise</p>	<p>I while shopping in the termina I lost track of time and I need to locate my self in the terminal. Mobile app or feature in terminal enduser app for navigation. System has Opt-in policy. Terminal has tracking points, sensors or QR code to provide tracing of the users movements and provide indor navigation to desired points.</p>
<p>User org. needs to have doc</p>	<p>As a system operator I want to documentation of the different components of the smart terminal system so that I can explain system properties in auditing</p>	<p>When auditing is in process system need to provide detailed documentation in every level of system architecture. Also 3rd party components needs to be documented or at least links to those systems documentation needs to available</p>

<p>Do I understand where I am in relation to the rest of the system?</p>	<p>As smart terminal service provider I want to understand my services relation to others so that I can integrate my service to the smart terminal with out causing chaos or service don't time</p>	<p>System needs to provide process documentation and specs for new service joining the system. List of acceptable actions should be given. E.g. are there restrictions of data usage, bandwidth, number of API queries...</p>
<p>Relevance for the systems user</p>	<p>As I annoyed User I want to understand why the terminal apps are showing me information of the service traceability so that I can be not annoyed or get rig of the popups</p>	<p>System needs to provide user friendly and short description of the traceability features of the service and also provide instructions to take acting to access traceability. System needs also be able to end user notifications on traceability if user wishes so</p>
<p>User org. can define demands</p>	<p>As Smart terminal service provider I want to have traceability on the smart terminal services usage and user demands so that I can focus service development efforts</p>	<p>Smart terminal system need to have API for BI tool so that the service provider can track the service usage.</p>
<p>Demand for traceability</p>	<p>As a government official, I want to trace the actions of the smart terminal, so that I can find out if its actions are acceptable</p>	<p>System should create explicit action log of its actions. The logs should be accessible for designated personnel and understandable or reliably interpretable for government or other officials who require the logs for a legitimate reason</p>
<p>user exclusivity (foreign and elder people e.g.)</p>	<p>As terminal elder aid provider I want to track the aid resources and coming customers so that I can direct required help where need</p>	<p>Systems identifies users with special need and has feature to inform terminal service provider of required help. Systems also need to be available to tract special need aids inside the terminal</p>

Technology or Practicality centric (e.g. testing, back-up, systems, logistics)

<p>I.) AI functionality should be based on requirements and specs, so it should be transparent information on how AI works and why it does what it does.</p>	<p>As an employee trying to fix an error of the AI system, I want to be able to find out why the AI did what it did, so that I can correct its behavior</p>	<p>AI system needs to have a function to generate an explanation for its actions if requested by a system administrator with rights to access the system</p>
<p>II.) According to normal SW development process.</p>	<p>As an employee trying to fix an error of the AI system, I want to be able to find out why the AI did what it did, so that I can correct its behavior</p>	<p>Function level documentation needs to be in place.</p>
<p>III.) You should have versatile use cases, which you are validating at the end.</p>	<p>As software developer I want to test my system with multiple use case so that I can reassure the client that the system is doing with it says it does.</p>	<p>System needs to be tested with given number of versatile use cases and not only obvious use cases with acceptable results. Also, those cases that would be possible but not testes should be clearly stated</p>
<p>Traceability for price</p>	<p>As a customer, I would like information on freight prices to enable me plan my budget</p>	<p>When planning my budget for freighting my goods, I would like clear information on the different pricing options (aggregated prices) maybe in an app, sites or displayboards at the terminal to help me plan my budget effectively.</p>
<p>Pricing criteria</p>	<p>As a passenger who uses the booking system, I would like clear and well defined pricing criteria to give me the necessary information I need.</p>	<p>clear and well defined pricing criteria such as pricing analysis for customers on the system</p>

<p>Interaction between physical and virtual spaces - how can the user orientate and be assisted through</p>	<p>As a customer, (older customer), I would like to know if I am relating to a human or machine to help me know how to channel my inquiries</p>	<p>When making inquiries as a customer, are there pointers to say you are communicating with a virtual assistant and is there provision for a human assistant where possible?</p>
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Data & information centric

<p>Data traceability</p>	<p>As auditor I want to understand what kind of data was used for the system so that I can be sure the data is representative for the given use context</p>	<p>When asked system documentation need to have description on what kind of data and from where was used to teach the system. Data set with out clear description should not be used</p>
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<p>XAI</p>	<p>As system developer I want to understand how the AI component works so that I can understand what causes the error in the system.</p>	<p>In service critical or human relating features only explainable AI/ML solutions are used. When requested the system can provide reasoning behind given result.</p>
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<p>Needs to be transparent for the users - what the software needs to do; information from the people, process and give outputs</p>	<p>As a passenger using the terminal I want to know that the data collected from me is used for the purpose i provide the data for</p>	<p>When prompted by passengers, the system should be able to provide information requested, eg customer asking for summary on a trip should be able to get one from the system</p>
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<p>Ethical aspects should be taken into account with GDPR, prior any implementation and then separately in each use case.</p>	<p>As an administrator of the system, I want to make sure that the system aligns with GDPR and the data is handled responsibly, so that the system is functioning legally</p>	<p>Before implementation, there should be a way to verify that the system is following the best practices and aligned with required legal standards</p>
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Why are you asking my data and for what	As a passenger using the terminal services, I want to know what data is collected of me and why, so that I can feel secure that my information is safe	A detailed document explaining the extent of the system's data use should be prepared and available to customers upon request.
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Data

7 Privacy and Data

Human centric(e.g. training, requirements, needs, goals, regulations)

How to provide data collection policy info	As a passenger I want to have clear and easily understandable policy notice on what personal data is collected from me and for what purpose and that I can opt in/out of "non-vital" policy info, if using an app with extended services like tracking my movements in the terminal.	The user is offered an easy to read statement of data privacy policies exercised with the terminal services for the services she is using (off the app) . She can opt in and out of data collection not necessary for my need of services.
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Dilemma between regulation and what is being collected	As a privacy officer in a stakeholder company joining the smart terminal, I want to make sure that the system is only collecting data it is allowed to, so that my company does not get any legal repercussions	System provides Data collection description and Data restrictions. Relevant contact information. Way to notify errors
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Can data be sell to others?	As a passenger, I want to know if the data stored of me in my use of the terminal can be sold to third parties, so I feel secure with my agency over my identifying information	Clear security communication to passengers who intend to use the terminal services, about what data is collected and how it is used
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<p>Anonymization and other measures (e.g. providing video surveillance in restricted area and during restricted time) are recommended to overcome GDPR violation possibilities.</p>	<p>As a passenger, I want to make sure that my personal identifying data is not available to everyone in the system so that I can feel safe it's not being misused</p>	<p>Video recordings and such unanonymized identifying data are only available to few certified people</p>
<p>Information on who has access to user data, is it used for marketing, statistics?</p>	<p>As a data privacy officer (or similar role) I want a registry of use purposes for different personal data "contents" is maintained and use of data is explained by the requirements set for data privacy notice and this information is maintained so I can ensure that the personal data use cases are communicated for the end user and their consents received, where applicable.</p>	<p>A register of personal data processing activities and their justification (basis for processing) is created, all involved parties are identified and this register is maintained and made available for needing parties.</p>
<p>informing users and giving them options</p>	<p>As a passenger I want to have one "info sheet" of data privacy, which is easy to read and not too long, so I can understand what purposes the data I provide is used for.</p>	<p>The data privacy notice is made available to the passenger (via the app she is using), which provides the purposes the personal data is used for.</p>
<p>GDPR clearance needs to be done in the beginning of the project</p>	<p>As I use case coordinator I want to understand of the systems and components contributing to the smart terminal system so that I can ask if GDPR clearances are needed and have the relevant system provide dealt with them</p>	<p>Use case coordinator has detailed plan of the systems and components contributing to the smart terminal system and also disclosure from those parties if they need GDPR clearances.</p>

Control over data	As a passenger I want to have control over the data which is not fundamentally "minimum needed for the travel service", so I can opt in or out of data collection per my preference to share data with the operator. Later I want the option to "delete" the data, which the operator has no legal basis to maintain, as per GDPR data subject rights.	The value add application the passenger is using needs to implement a control which identifies, which data processing activities are necessary for which basic or added value services the user is considering to use and she can thus opt in or out of the service based on the data processed. The data the user has selected for her rights execution needs to be processed accordingly, e.g. anonymized, deleted or made available for the user to transfer to another service/download.
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Why is the data collected? Is it for safety and security of the passengers.	As a VIP passenger I want to understand why is the data collected so that I can trust my VIP data with the system	Data statements need to be available and also descriptions what services optional and how to opt—out on those need to be implanted. Description of what parts of the system are used by harbor official and cannot by opt-outed
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IF there is a risk for data breach, that needs to be clarified in DPIA and end users need to be informed on possibility for GDPR violation.	As Concerned smart terminal data security office I want to cover possible risks in DPIA so that I can be sure that privacy and data breach has been considered by the system providers	DPIA must be made to meet the given standards. Relevant stakeholders for the SMART terminal system need to be informed about the required level of standards for Data and privacy when operating as a part of SMART terminal system
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Technology or Practicality centric (e.g. testing,back-up, systems, logistics)

Data layers?	As enthusiastic sw developer I want understand the SMART terminal systems data layers so that I know on which layer my service can operate and what data sources are available or me	System architecture needs to be draw and it needs to be shareable with relevant stakeholders. Possible security issues relating to architecture information sharing needs to be mitigated
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Passenger flow video, security, immigration, transit hall wifi?	As a passenger using the terminal I want to be assured that all the data gathered on me from all these sources are used in line with GDPR and not used out of context	The system can notify users on their tickets and display boards that data being collected are used in line with GDPR. Also regular testing and security checks to ensure that customer data are not being jeopardized
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Mask detection - everyone wants another process: what biometrics can be used around a mask?	As a passenger using the terminal and I have religious beliefs where I have to cover my face, and now with the use of masks I want to know that the system has another way of identifying me besides me showing my face	Other forms of biometrics such as iris or finger print recognition as an alternative to facial recognition
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Network penetration tests are typically required to ensure sufficient cyber security of the system, to minimize data breach risk.	As a cyber security officer, I want to do everything to ensure that the system is secure, so that our data does not get stolen	A regular testing protocol should be in place, to ensure the security of the system and protect against threats. The system should be kept updated and its resilience tested in regular intervals
How to accurately capturing data?	As an administrator of the system, I want to ensure the data processed by the system is accurate, so that the data is good quality for several purposes	Protocols for verifying that the system collects data accurately should be in place. The data accuracy and quality should be evaluated on a regular basis

Data & information centric

What kind of data does the smart harbor produce?	As an administrator, I would like to ensure that the data the harbor produce are accurate to provide safe and economical services for cargo and passenger travels.	Ensure that channels used for data collection document processes to aid accuracy
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What data would be valuable from a company and marketing point of view? If it improves the service offered, it may be fine.	As an administrator, I would like transport system-related data to help improve the transport services of the smart terminal	Secure APIs to help enable the process and open data sources
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<p>What kind bought data would benefit smart harbors</p>	<p>As a data analyst (or the appropriate role) using the bought data for the system, I would like to know that the data are of good quality and not biased so that I can provide an effective and unbiased service for users of the system</p>	<p>Documentation and logs of data sources for traceability</p>
<p>What data is relevant for smart terminals?</p>	<p>As a data analyst (appropriate role), I would like to have data that helps with transport services and customer analysis to help me provide data relevant for the terminal</p>	<p>relevant Data sources (APIs) are open for data analyst from the system and not just generic data</p>
<p>there are also other regulations for viudeo surveillance, in addition to GDPR, which are related to personal data. GDPR clearance doesn't solve all issues with personal data, when video is handled</p>	<p>As a passenger using the terminal, I would like to know that there are regulations that govern how surveillance videos are used that will guarantee the privacy of videos I am in and only relevant users are granted access.</p>	<p>The system follows regulations on data privacy and ensures that data access is granted only to relevant personnel.</p>
<p>The way the purpose of collecting data also matters. If it is a long legal disc</p>	<p>As a passenger, I would like to know why my data is being collected so that it does not wind up being sold or appear somewhere I did not give my permission.</p>	<p>Passengers can be notified by the system at collection points such as on remote terminals, or if they use apps at point of feeding their data why their data is being collected</p>

Data lifecycle	<p>"As a passenger, I would like to know how long my data is kept by the system so that it is not kept indefinitely as this will give me peace of mind.</p> <p>As a data administrator(appropriate role), I would like to deal with data that are up to date or in line with regulations that have not exceeded their duration period as this will help me work with current and relevant data and at the same time let me know that I am not violating any regulations"</p>	Regular data checks embedded in system to notify appropriate personnel on lifecycle of data to ensure conformity to regulations
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Safety & Security

#12 System Security

Human centric(e.g. training, requirements, needs, goals, regulations)

Guidelines for strengthening the system, system needs to be monitored for vulnerabilities; pen-testing	As a passenger, I want to be able to trust that the system is a secure one, so that I will not be inconvenienced (or worse) by a cyber attack of some sort.	System is continuously monitored for vulnerabilities. Penetration tests have been conducted, and new ones are conducted as needed.
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Keeping the human in the loop. I. e ramps to ships	<p>"As a passenger, I want to still have some humans (from the company) around, so that I can talk to a human in case of problem situations / feel like the company cares about me.</p> <p>As an executive, I want to have a human in the loop, so that the employees can resolve any</p>	The extent of necessary human oversight has been determined. The employees in charge of overseeing the process have been appointed.
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	unforeseen issues and execute a contingency plan if needed."	
integration of several systems operated by several actors is challenging	As a CTO, I want the different systems that need to be integrated together to work seamlessly, so that the system functions correctly.	Systems have been integrated successfully.
Adversarial attacks on neural networks	As a CTO/CSO, I want the system to be safe not only from conventional cyber attacks but also cyber attacks specifically targeting the AI/neural network components of the system, so that system is secure against all types of attacks.	To protect against data pollution, e.g., disable the system from learning in use (offline). This is an on-going issue where solutions are evolving right now, and various measures should be considered.
Different security risk and requirements for different parts	As security auditor I want to have descriptions of different security risk and mitigation plans so that I can validate the system	Detailed security plan from architecture level to single system feature level is drawn and mitigation plan is in action
Planning and processes before security breach - PRE-INCIDENT readiness	As a security officer, I want the staff to know what to do in case of a security breach, so that they know how to minimize damage and react fast if an incident occurs	An action protocol should be prepared for the occasion of a successful security breach. The system should be tested and kept as invulnerable as possible, but the staff should also be trained to take action to minimize damage in case of a successful attack on the system